

THE ROLE OF THE YOUNG GENERATION IN INCREASING MILITARY PATRIOTISM

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Abstract:

Keywords:

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The future generation patriotism in the spirit education - the state bodies , team organizations and of associations in young people patriotism in the spirit in education purposeful , systematic and coordinated is an activity . From this main the goal young people in his mind citizenship position , social values and constitutional duties relatively loyalty feeling is formation .

Military patriotism mother of the country , of the people history and fate deep respect with looking after , Homeland interests on the way dedication samples to show able has been to young people special is a virtue . To the country , to the people has been respect , love , trust feeling certain common interests , goals based on formed , of people from the heart deep place takes , activity effect making them _ responsible tasks to perform mobile reached stands _ So , to say perhaps , patriotism - own fate homeland , nation destiny with connected all to people special is a virtue .

Uzbekistan Republic National guard organize from the first days from , his ranks rich in meaning , our values tradition and to our traditions loyal , physical strong and intellectual potential was young people attraction to do separately attention is being directed .

Uzbekistan Republic National guard command short time inside his own activities in order puter regulatory and legal documents preparation with one in line in the ranks each how in the circumstances public order and of the population safety protection to do able was personnel with to fill new , that is continuously personnel preparation system _ _ to put managed to Including Uzbekistan _ Republic National guard rank to fill for young people common medium education

from school starting from military patriotism in the spirit to educate separately attention was directed .

Today's in the day of our republic each one 4 in the region , total 56 total in the account medium education in their schools National guard system for personnel continuously and purposeful who prepares military patriotism direction specialized classes activity to the road was placed .

Uzbekistan Republic National of the guard main duties of the following consists of :

- cities and population points public order and of security to be kept in providing to help ;

- state importance have objects , vital important objects , foreign of states diplomatic , consular and another representative offices and physical and legal of individuals property guarding and protection to do

- terrorism and extremism of their actions prevention in getting participation reach _

- of the country territorial integrity and defense in providing participation reach _

- hunting and service shooter of weapons country to the territory take entry , take output , purchase to be made , to be kept and application control to do

- natural and man-made to the feature have was extraordinary of situations consequences eliminate in reaching to help ;

- foreign of states official representatives waiting get and in observation high level ceremony events provide .

Note of Uzbekistan _ different at the points National guard in the system all departments , military part , units , military servant and employees by special events organized .

Patriotism monthly within 1 month during city , district in the centers local population for military parade and festivals , music programs , weapons and military techniques demonstrations , running marathons , propaganda events and shares to be is passing .

From this except for this events different on the steps education institutions , kindness and please houses pupils for young generation patriotism in the spirit to educate directed military spiritual and educational events demonstration is being done .

National guard military servant and employees second the world war heroes and work veterans , service duty pass during death was of colleagues family members and social to the defense needs population representatives from message take them _ spiritual and material help showing they are coming

Our people own forward good and great goals _ let it be , in peace life First of all , he forgives himself strength and opportunities based on democratic state and citizenship society to build on the way huge the results to the hand entering in time is living Today's in the day Uzbek people own our fate ourselves define forever _ to our values developed based on countries experience account received without , prospective , noble aspirations with where we live , our people centuries during looking forward to expected free , free and prosperous life set up all that we are doing our capabilities and this on the way achieving our achievements international that the community recognized - that is , independence honor from being is evidence .

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